

Reflection on microteaching practice among health training institutions newly recruited tutors who attended teaching methodology short course at CEDHA, Arusha Tanzania: A qualitative study

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International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 15(03), 1040-1047

Publication history: Received on 18 March 2025; revised on 14 June 2025; accepted on 16 June 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.15.3.1226>

Abstract

Introduction: Microteaching is technique which helps the teacher trainee to master the teaching skills by practice teaching with a reduced number of pupils in a reduced period of time with emphasis on a narrow and specific teaching skill.

Objective: The study examined the views of newly recruited HTI tutors on microteaching practice

Method: A qualitative method where open ended question survey approach was used

Results: The study findings revealed that micro teaching practice has provided an opportunity for newly HTI recruited tutors to: improve their facilitation skills, confidence, use of teaching materials and teaching aids and expand their network in teaching and learning

Conclusion: Newly recruited HTI tutors revealed that micro teaching has improved their teaching competencies

It recommended that all newly recruited HTI Tutors should attend this course just before they start teaching

Keywords: Microteaching; Facilitation skills; Tutors; Health training institution(HTI)

1. Introduction

1.1. Micro-teaching (Teach Back)

Teacher training technique which helps the teacher trainee to master the teaching skills or micro teaching is a procedure in which a learner teacher practices teaching with a reduced number of pupils in a reduced period of time with emphasis on a narrow and specific teaching skill.

Microteaching requires the teacher trainee to; teach a single concept of content and Use a specified teaching skill for a short time and a very small number of learners.

The purposes of microteaching are; to enable teacher trainees to learn and assimilate new teaching skills under controlled conditions, to enable teacher trainees to master a number of teaching skills and to enable teacher trainees to gain confidence in teaching. Micro-teaching cycle generally involves six steps ; Plan, Teach, and Feedback, Re-plan, Re-

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teach, Re-feedback. There can be variations as per requirement of the objective of practice session. These Steps are described as follows:

1.1.1. Step 1: Plan

This involves the selection of the topic and related content of such a nature in which the use of components of the skill under practice may be made easily and conveniently. The topic is analyzed into different activities of the teacher and the learners. The activities are planned in such a logical sequence where maximum application of the components of a skill is possible.

1.1.2. Step 2: Teach

This involves the attempts of the teacher trainee to use the components of the skill in suitable situations coming up in the process of teaching-learning as per his/her planning of activities. If the situation is different and not as visualized (in the planning of the activities, the teacher should modify his/her behaviour as per the demand of the situation in the class. He should have the courage and confidence to handle the situation arising in the class effectively.

1.1.3. Step 3: Feedback

This term refers to giving information to the teacher trainee about his performance. The information includes the points of strength as well as weakness relating to his/her performance. This helps the teacher trainee to improve upon his/her performance in the desired direction.

1.1.4. Step 4: Re-plan

The teacher trainee re-plans his lesson incorporating the points of strength and removing the points not skilfully handled during teaching in the previous attempt either on the same topic or on another topic suiting to the teacher trainee for improvement.

1.1.5. Step 5: Re-teach

This involves teaching to the same group of pupils if the topic is changed or to a different group of pupils if the topic is the same. This is done to remove boredom or monotony of the pupil. The teacher trainee teaches the class with renewed courage and confidence to perform better than the previous attempt.

1.1.6. Step 6: Re-feedback

This is the most important component of Micro-teaching for behaviour modification of teacher trainee in the desired direction in each and every skill practice. ^[1-3]

1.2. Reflective in Practice Theory (RPT)

Reflective practice is theory and process of learning by examining and reflecting on one's own experience and actions. It's a continuous cycle of self-observation, critical analysis and improvement, based on the idea that experience alone isn't enough for learning but reflection on experience is crucial.

This process helps learners develop a deep understanding of their work and refine their skills. It bridges gap between theatrical knowledge and practical by allowing practitioner to see how theory informs their work and vice versa.

The reflective in practice theory is premised on skillful strategies to solving real-world problems. It is a non-technical epistemology that requires individuals to deeply explore and test assumptions and attend to the context as they encounter problematic situations. Naming and framing are parts of the process by which practitioners come to understand what is going on in practical situations. What distinguishes reflection-in-action from technical-rationality model of practice is that knowledge in the former is inherently practical and contextual based while in the later knowledge is systematically and theory driven.

The RPT draws largely on coaching, learning by doing and reflective practicum as central elements to reflection in-action epistemology and the professional growth. This presupposes that both professionals and would be professionals need coaching and learning by doing in their daily practices instead of relying on professional technical skills that do not acknowledge the context and uniqueness of the situation they encounter. By reflective practicum students learn by doing and by the help of their mentors. Learning by doing serves two purposes that include enabling students to become

proficient in a kind of reflection-in-action and by dialogue between the mentor and student, a reciprocal reflection-in-action (thinking what they are doing while they are doing it) is enhanced. [4].

The major objectives of micro teaching include enabling teacher trainees to learn and assimilate new teaching skills under controlled environment or conditions.

Microteaching aimed to enables HTI newly recruited tutors to master a number of teaching skills which empower them to gain confidence in teaching. Micro teaching is geared towards equipping new tutor trainees to gain confidence in teaching.

While microteaching is made up of some characteristics, new tutors were are required toPractice six common facilitations skill for a short time, teach a single concept and use the skill on a very small number of pupils.

It is well known that microteaching is a real teaching situation where the complexity of the real classroom teaching is reduced. It is microteaching in terms; time (duration), class size (population) and content (task to be accomplished). The teacher trainees who are regarded as the micro-teachers teach between 5-10 students who are likely to be their fellow students, colleagues, classmates and friends for 15 to 20 minutes instead of facing the real classroom situation of about 40 to 50 students. Instead of teaching for 60 to 120 minutes per session

The key microteaching skills practiced during microteaching were ; classroom management, set induction and closure, stimulus variation ,reinforcement explaining and questioning skills. [1-3].

1.3. Objective

Assess perception of newly recruited HTI tutors on microteaching practice during short course on teaching methodology in improving their teaching skills.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

This study employed qualitative approach, open ended question survey was used to capture views of newly recruited HTI tutors regarding micro teaching practice. Each participants were asked to write on: What are your reflection on the microteaching practice?.

2.2. Study setting

The study was conducted at centre for educational development in health Arusha (CEDHA), established in 1983 by Ministry of Health to equip teaching staff with educational, managerial and research skills for them to be better teachers and managers in HTIs. The teaching methodology is tailor made short course from long standing course only offered at CEDHA Health personnel education (HPE) program ,a one year course with seven modules and offered in two semesters from which was developed to suit the needs of the medical teachers in Health Training Institutions (HTIs). The programme aims at. This program is only offered at Centre for Educational Development in Health Arusha (CEDHA) which was aimed at strengthening and supports the health care system. [5-6].

2.3. Targeted population

All newly recruited HTI tutors who attended teaching methodology short course training at CEDHA April 2025 were involved.

2.4. Data collection method

All newly recruited HTI tutors who attended short course training on teaching methodology were given plain sheet of paper to write on their reflection on the microteaching practice conducted a day before, all paper were collected after 30 minutes

2.5. Data analysis

Thematic analysis was used to analyse qualitative data set capture by gathering participants' reflection on microteaching. It involves the identification of themes through careful reading and re-reading of the transcribed data. [7].The following steps were conducted manually:

2.5.1. Step 1: Familiarization

Researcher went through collected data set from all 23 participants so as to know the data before start analyzing them. This involved reading through the text from all participants and taking initial notes

2.5.2. Step 2: Coding

Next step was to highlight sections of collected text from participants by phrases or sentences and came up with shorthand labels or “codes” to describe their content.

The total of eleven codes was identified, as shown below:

- Thanks for chance to study at CEDHA
- Welcoming institution
- Thanks facilitators
- Facilitation skills
- Gained confidence
- Networking
- Use of laptop during presentation
- Use of curriculum and lesson plan
- Facilitators worked as team
- Good in Teaching
- Teaching environment was clean

2.5.3. Step 3: Generating themes

Researcher looked over the created codes and identified patterns among them and combined several codes came up with themes that are generally broader than codes. Six themes were generated out of the eleven identified codes

Table 1 Codes and their themes

Codes	Themes
Thanked for chance to study at CEDHA Welcoming institution Teaching environment was clean	Conducive training environment
Thanks facilitators Facilitators worked as team Good in Teaching	Competent facilitators
Facilitation skills	Facilitation skills and methods
Gained confidence	Gained confidence
Use of laptop during presentation Use of curriculum and lesson plan	Use of teaching aids and materials
Networking	Networking

- All codes were relevant and appeared very often in the data so no code was discarded.
- Other codes became themes in their own right. In our example, we decided that the code “gained confidence” and “networking” made sense as a themes, while other codes combined together to make sense.

2.5.4. Step 4: Reviewing themes

After making sure that themes are useful and accurate representations of the collected qualitative data. Here, themes were compared against data set, and researcher was sure that; there was no missed information and the created themes really presented in the data. So only code “networking” was changed and created theme “Expand working network”

Table 2 Reviewed Themes

Created themes	Reviewed themes (changing terminology)
Conducive training environment	Conducive training environment
Competent facilitators	Competent facilitators
Facilitation skills and methods	Facilitation skills and methods
Gained confidence	Gained confidence
Use of teaching aids and materials	Use of teaching aids and materials
Networking	Expand working network

2.5.5. Step 5: Defining and naming themes

The themes were then named and defined have a final list of themes; defining themes involved formulating exactly what we mean by each theme and figuring out how it helps us understand the collected qualitative data while naming themes involved coming up with a concise and easily understandable name for each theme.

Table 3 Defined and named themes

Reviewed themes	Defined and named themes
Conducive training environment	Microteaching was conducted in conducive working environment
Competent facilitators	Microteaching was facilitated by competent facilitators
Facilitation skills and methods	Microteaching has improved my facilitation skills
Gained confidence	Microteaching has improved my confidence
Use of teaching aids and materials	Microteaching has improved my skills on using teaching materials and teaching aids
Expand working network	Microteaching has expand my working network

3. Results

The results from an open ended survey question on reflection to twenty three newly recruited HTI tutors, who practiced microteaching practice conducted a day before data collection while attending teaching methodology short course were analysed using thematic analysis and the following themes were identified: Microteaching was conducted in conducive working environment, Microteaching was facilitated by competent facilitators, Microteaching has improved my facilitation skills, Microteaching has improved my confidence, Microteaching has improved my skills on using teaching materials and teaching aids and Microteaching has expand my working network.

3.1. Microteaching was conducted in conducive working environment

This study find out that one third of the participant reported that the environment was conducive for microteaching practice and teaching methodology short course training. The findings imply that CEDHA is well established HTI with long standing experience in training established in 1983. [5-6].

Participants, P16 reported that “when I was coming here at CEDHAI had no detailed idea of what I was coming to learn. In a simple way I was vocational learner, but on the long run of training I become more interested and gained a lot. Thanks to CEDHA”

This perception was also written by another participant, P13 who described training environment as follows: “Training was enjoyable, well and good welcoming by our facilitators, cooperative and competent facilitator who are competent in teaching methodology, I really appreciate your lovely mentors, God bless you”

3.2. Microteaching was facilitated by competent facilitators

Half of participants revealed that microteaching was facilitated by competent facilitators, this reflects the fact that CEDHA has a long-standing history of facilitating teaching and learning long and short courses ever since establishment, the available teaching team has participated in a number of trainings in the country. [5].

A competent facilitator uses different activities to make trainees active, awake, attentive and stimulated throughout the learning process. These activities are called facilitation skills, the common facilitation skills are; stimulus variation, questioning, reinforcement, explaining and classroom management, induction and closure.

Stimulus variation is the process of changing manner or personal teaching style, media of communicating and ways of interacting with learners. Arouse and sustain learners' attention to relevant aspects of teaching and learning.

A trainee P1, described the facilitators' teaching skills she had experienced by participating in micro-teaching as follows: *"In the past training I thought I have a concentration problem.....I never concentrated in my training journey, I used to sleep a lot, like every sessionI fought about it but I failed. I admitted that, that was the way I am....But in this training I have been very very attentive, concentrating and not sleepingFacilitators have used various techniques to keep us attentive and active."*

Although studies have demonstrated a lack of facilitation skills among tutors and clinical instructors for implementing competence-based education and training programs in Tanzania. [8].

3.3. Microteaching has improved my facilitation skills

One third of the participants who attended this short course in microteaching admitted the experience they got from microteaching, that they learned how to control learners of different types and personalities, to control teaching resources and manage time. They also appreciated other skills like how to start and end a session, application of stimulus variation, use of reinforcement, explaining and asking questions. Studies have shown that the microteaching practice improves pre-service teachers' skills in teaching. [9-10].

Newly recruited HTI P7, who attended the microteaching had this to write as his reflection on microteaching practice: *"I have learned how to use facilitation skills like reinforcement skill when facilitating sessions...and also the use of energizers, initially I thought they are of NO importance but now I know the importance of using them in Teaching."*

3.4. Microteaching has improved my confidence

It is documented that practicing microteaching improves pre-service confidence in handling teaching and learning activities [9].

One third of the newly recruited HTI tutors who practiced microteaching believed that micro-teaching helped them to develop self-confidence and that they will be able to speak up in the classroom.

Furthermore, they agreed that micro-teaching helped them to increase their confidence level. The purpose of microteaching is to reduce nervousness of the new tutors by teaching a small content for a short time and to a small group of colleagues.

A participant P12 when describing the skills she has acquired during the microteaching session he said:

"I remember when I started teaching, I was not confident to facilitate sessions...it was not easy because I had no skills nor strategies for teaching effectively... as no teaching training attended before."

3.5. Microteaching has improved my skills on using teaching materials and teaching aids

Newly recruited HTI tutors revealed that they had a chance to learn and practice the use of teaching materials and teaching aids during the microteaching session.

Health learning materials are any materials e.g. books, manuals, posters, flip charts, slides, films, teachers' guides, self-instructional packages, designed to help teachers and, students and health workers in the field to improve their skills and competence.

These resources are used by a trainer, instructors, facilitators, and students in a training environment. These materials store the information needed by the learner to perform tasks, so facilitators should have skills for effective use of these resources.

A newly recruited HTI tutor P3 reflected that: *"I have learned how to use teaching aids like; projector, computer, lesson plan curriculum and facilitator guides...I was not oriented on these when I started teaching one month ago... I am happy I have attended this course."*

The effect of microteaching on use of teaching aids was also noted by pre service teachers in the study on the Influence of Micro-Teaching in Enhancing Teaching Competences of Pre-Service Teachers: who revealed that; Micro-Teaching assisted them to learn how to use the blackboard effectively [9].

3.6. Microteaching has expand my working network

Social Learning Theorist in trying to explain how animals including we human being learn, they pointed out that, interactions between people is the primary mechanism of learning. Humans learn best in group activities, with assumptions that; People learn by observing the behaviour of others and the outcomes of those behaviours. Learning is based on observation of others in a social setting and People learn from one another and not in isolation from others. The facilitators manage to use this theory in facilitating the training by making sure that the participant interact as much as possible and eventually one quarter of learners revealed that they had chance to network. [1-3].

The participant P2 had this to write: *"I have gained new friends from other HTI ... they made learning to be easy for me. I promise I will cooperate with them even after this training on training and social issues to improve my experience in teaching and learning."*

Limitations

The responses are qualitative in nature, making it challenging to generalize findings to a large population. Vague responses were generated like the high fee for the course which were irrelevant to study objective

4. Conclusion and recommendation

Thus, in the light of the findings presented and discussed above, it can be concluded that, newly recruited HTI tutors have revealed that micro teaching improved their teaching competencies. Therefore is a need for all newly recruited HTI Tutors to attend this course just before they start teaching.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Newly recruited HTI tutors who attended teaching methodology short course in April, 2025 at CEDHA and agreed to give their reflection about microteaching practice.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares that he has no competing interests financial and non - financial.

Statement of ethical approval

Ethics approval for this study has been granted by the Center for Educational Development in Health Arusha (CEDHA).

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Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was sought from participants and they were assured of the right to refuse to participate or to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

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